

Descriptions of the variables in the dataset

20210324_SubSetData.csv	
eticiteitnieuw3	Ethnicity background in 2 categories (1 = West EU, 2 = Turkish/Moroccan)
geslacht	Gender (0 = girl, 1 = boy)
Q4	School id
EthnicComposition	Percentage of students speaking a language other than Dutch at home
onderwijstype	Educational Track (1 = ASO, 2 = TSO, 3 = BSO)
opleidingouders	Educational Level of Parents (1 = Low, 2 = Middle, 3 = High, 4 = Other)
Diversiteitmean	Mean score of Multicultural Dimension in Curriculum
LesEUmean	Mean score of European Dimension in Curriculum
EuropeseIDmean	Mean score of European identity